

A Study on Marketing Strategies and Customers Satisfaction towards Health Drinks - with Special Reference to Tiruchirappalli District

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Abstract

The present day customers is said to enjoy dominion in the market. The access of marketing depends upon the ability of the marketer to satisfy his customers. The drinks sector in India has undergone important transformation in previous times 10 years. The drinks industry in India is togrow near about 45 per cent annually and would triple or four times in size by2014. Customer favorites are more complex and even more important forretailers today than in past.The customer's favorites pertaining to the various product of health drink. Basically we intend to find out the most popular flavor, what factor compels to consume (like product, advertisement, quality, variants), product rating (like excellent, good, average, poor), what size prefer most in the terms of packing how often consume it, what is the source of information regarding the purchase of it, do health drink come up with more flavor in the market from our sample.

Introduction

The behavior of a customers is dynamic and not static. In the olden days customers was not aware of the variety of products due to ignorance and absence of proper media and marketing process. They used to buy what was sold in the market rather than what should be bought according to their favorites. The trend has changed now. The customers are the real masters of the market. They buy only the product, which satisfies their need, taste and favorites depending upon their income, expected price and product satisfaction. Thus satisfaction of customers is the essence of modern marketing concept.

Before proceeding further a word customersism is very much relevant. "Customer a social movement seeking to augment the rights and powers of buyers in relation to sellers". Consumption of coffee, Tea and soft drinks is a recent development and has become a part and parcel of human life.

Health drinks are a class of non-alcoholic drinks usually containing sweetening agents, edible acids and natural (or) artificial flavours derived from fruits, berries, herbs, plant, sources etc., Coffee, Tea, Milk and undiluted fruit and vegetable juices are not considered as soft drinks.

The term of “Health Drinks”, is ordinarily associated with flavored light refreshment. The drinks like Lemon, Orange, Grapes, Rose, Cherry, and Ginger Toxic without flavoring (or) sweetening agent are known as soda. They may contain minerals salts also to some extent.

Health drinks are generally preferred by all customers. As the saying goes, ‘a health drink refreshes like no other’. Soft drinks with its modern form came to capture the market in 1950. Step by step, Soft drinks stand at a high altitude today. Favorites is just a manifestation of the changing mind in the sense it has to be understood psychologically. The interest evinced by the customers is the outcome of a gradual increase in the demand and supply rapport.

Customers at present are well informed and have a wider knowledge of products available, their price, quality, utility value etc., they are provided with a wide choice of health drinks and are at freely to choose from range of product alternatives, depending upon their fulfillment derived from the products.

The health-drink industry includes companies that manufacture non alcoholic drinks and carbonated mineral waters or concentrates and syrups for the manufacture of carbonated drinks. Health drink products have been well accepted by customers and gradually overtaking hot drinks as the biggest beverage sector in the world. The rapid growth of health drinks depends up on public demands; the industry on the whole is facing new opportunities and challenges. Changing customers’ demands and favorites require new ways of maintaining current customers and attracting new ones. Safety and keep prices low all while staying nimble enough to exploit new markets by launching new products. Recent developments in health drinks consumption and challenges in marketing have finely tuned the customers’ needs and satisfaction.

Customers Contentment

Customers favorites is used primarily to mean to select an option that has the greatest anticipated value among a number of options by the customers in order to satisfy his/her needs or desires. Favorites indicate choices among neutral or more valued options available. The preference of the customers is the result of their behaviour they show during searching, purchasing and disposing the products.

Customers favorites are defined as the subjective (individual) tastes, as measured by utility, of various bundles of goods. They permit the customers to rank these bundles of goods according to the levels of utility they give the customers. The favorite’s are self-determining of income and prices. Ability to purchase goods does not determine customers’ likes or dislikes. In other words, the customers has different favorites over the different combinations of goods defined by the set of commodity bundles.

Customers favorites are measured in terms of the level of satisfaction the customer obtains from consuming various combinations or bundles of goods. The customer’s objective is to choose the bundle of goods which provides the greatest level of satisfaction as they the customers define it. But customers are very much constrained in their choices. These constraints are defined by the customers income, and the prices the customers pays for the goods. Customers value is measured in terms of the relative utilities between goods and these reflect the customers’s favorites.

Objective of the Study

- (i) To study the profile of health drink customers.
- (ii) To find out the factors influencing product preference.
- (iii) To enquire into buying behavioural pattern of the health drink customers.
- (iv) To assess the impact of advertisement of the product preference of health drink among the customers.
- (v) To analyze the level of satisfaction of the health drink customers.

Scope of the Study

In a business world, many products of health drinks are produced and marketed by a single manufacturer. The decision whether to buy or not depends only a customer motive. Modern Market is customer oriented and how customers are decisive force. The foresaid reason has inspired the researcher to make out a study about the factors influencing product preference buying behavior and level of satisfaction of the customers.

The product preferential of the costumer, buying behaviour, attitudes of the customer towards the price, taste, flavor, quality, level of satisfaction, and the impact of advertisement.

Statement of the Problem

The Indian soft drink market is very wide and big to control, as India has all types of seasons and different locations with different cultures. Soft drinks industry is a massive industry with a stiff competition. All People, irrespective of their age & earning, customer. Soft drinks and is interested in making their own choice of soft drink product.

In Modern business world, due to the development of Science and technology, any new product of products floods the market every year. When the new product enter to the market, some customers switchover to it. Hence, a study need on product preference becomes necessary.

The researcher is interested in investigating, all the factors that influence the preference of product. The researcher was interested to know the impact of advertisement, buying behavioural pattern and satisfaction level of the customers.

Research Methodology

The questionnaire was prepared for the purpose of data collection. The questionnaire includes personal background information of the customers; factors influencing product favorite, purchasing behaviour, reasons for expenditure, place of purchase made, media influence opinion about health drinks advertisement and the level of satisfaction

Sources of Data

Table 1

S. No	Gender wise details	No. of Respondents
1	Male	300
2	Female	200
Total		500

The above table reveals the Gender wise of the total respondents is 500. The Highly usages of health drinks in male is higher.

Table 2
Health Drinks Wise Details

S. No	Health Drinks wise respondents	No. of Respondents
1	Satisfied	350
2	Not Satisfied	150
Total		500

The above table shows the health Drinks wise of the respondents established their views highly satisfied. Hence the consumer mostly prefers health drinks and hot drinks are fully satisfied.

Table 3
Customer Satisfaction level of health drinks

S. No	Satisfaction level of Customers	No. of Respondents
1	Satisfied	100
2	Not satisfied	100
3	Dissatisfied	50
4	Highly Satisfied	200
5	Highly Not Satisfied	50
Total		500

Most of the Respondents were used among health drinks wise either satisfied or highly satisfied. Hence the table signifies the no of respondents were in neutral.

Table 4
Product Rating of Health Drinks Wise Details

S. No	Product Rating	No. of Respondents
1	Excellent	200
2	Good	150
3	Average	70
4	Poor	30
5	Very Poor	50
Total		500

The Product Rating of Health Drinks Wise is outstanding and better-quality of the customer's views. Hence Some of the Customer the rating wise of health drinks is reduced.

The Sample

The study was conducted on 500 respondents. The sampling method was random convenience sampling. The variables are

Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant impact or difference in mean fulfillment level of customers taste and preference of the users.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is significant impact or difference in mean satisfaction level of customers because of satisfied and not satisfied health drinks factors.

Limitation of the Study

The researcher has some limitations in his execution, which are enlisted below:

- (i) Due to cost and time constraints information was collected
- (ii) There only certain familiar products chosen in this study.
- (iii) This deals with the information supplied by the respondents and hence it can't be depending upon wholly.

Conclusion

Finally this study to look at the Customers taste and preference, with respect of health drinks in and to variations in the customer's favorites with respect health drinks wise. In addition, this study shows that the average customer of in the towns and our sample was not very cognizant about health drinks, but gender wise they are also aware about any types of customer's satisfaction. They are coming stores for purchasing drinks but for getting drink and taste.